

Opinion: The correct way to analyze FP signals

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NOTE: this text is designed to be iterative, with a full version control showing changes for the sake of transparency, and therefore, I state:

These are my principles, and if you don't like them...

well, I can always adopt others (if you scientifically prove that I am wrong)!¹

Here, I summarize my thoughts after several years of analyzing field potential (FP) signals from 2D human induced pluripotent stem cells derived cardiomyocyte (hiPSC-CM) cultures (Häkli et al. 2021; Häkli et al. 2022 and several other yet unpublished data). While developing a software, named as *DatAnalyzer*², to analyze these FP-signals, I noticed that they have been analyzed so many different ways in the literature. And many times, I just did not understand, why some publications implemented one analysis method whereas other publications used (more or less) totally different approaches. While struggling to understand these sometimes pretty challenging FP-signals, I really missed a comprehensive summary of their analysis; therefore, I wanted to wrap up my own understanding.

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Abbreviations

In this text, the following abbreviations are used

- **A0** = baseline amplitude

- **A_{low}** = low peak amplitude
- **A_{peak}** = peak amplitude, typically A₀-A_{low}
- **AP** = action potential
- **ARI** = activation-recovery interval
- **A_{rep}** = repolarization peak amplitude
- **APD** = action potential duration
- **BPM** = beats per minute, here basically how fast hiPSC-CMs culture is beating
- **CM** = cardiomyocyte
- **DAD** = delayed afterdepolarization
- **EAD** = early afterdepolarization
- **ECG** = electrocardiogram
- **FP** = field potential, signal of the beating cardiomyocyte(s) measured by MEA
- **FPD** = field potential duration, length of the beating (in sec or msec)
- **hiPSC-CMs** = human induced pluripotent stem cells derived CMs
- **MEA** = multielectrode array, method to measure FP
- **MPS** = microphysiological systems
- **QT** = QT interval, time from the start of the Q wave to the end of the T wave from ECG
- **RW** = repolarization width
- **t_{dep}** = depolarization time

Summary

I claim, that the most common ways to analyze MEA signals measured from beating *in vitro* CM cultures (= FP signal from now on in this text) are wrong. In the examples, I mainly use MEA signals recorded from beating *in vitro* hiPSC-CM cultures. However, these claims are valid for MEA recorded FP-signals from other, at least 2D, beating CM cultures as well. Analyzing FP-signals, I show how

- depolarization should be understood from FP-signals
- signals that do not have "typical" form should be modified for the further analysis
- FPD should be estimated
- defining more parameters from signals will provide better analysis
- template matching or AI "magic" for **raw** FP-signals might not work, thus propose a new method

My opinion is: **do not analyze MEA-measurements** this way.

Figure1: The most common, but imprecise way to analyze FP signals. Left figure is adapted from Tertoolen et al. (2018).

Instead, you **should analyze them** as I present in the following. In a propagating hiPSC-CM monolayer, the first positive peak is not depolarization of the local (main) cell, it is coming from the depolarization of neighbor cell(s)! And, the end of FPD should be defined as a time instant when the repolarization peak is returned back to the baseline, not where the repolarization peak is found. Note that this baseline-return convention captures complete repolarization (extending into the APD95-100 range), which is a distinct quantity from the T-wave peak that corresponds to APD90; the choice of convention depends on which physiological target is relevant.

Figure2: My opinion, how FP signals should be analyzed. FPD is calculated as time between points 0' to 4'.

Now you might wonder, why all this hassle, who cares?!

For example, EAD might not be possible to notice during FP-analysis if the end of FPD is defined as the repolarization peak, not as the end of repolarization wave. Examples of EAD in AP-signals are shown e.g. in Fig.1 (Wolf and Berul 2008; Xie et al. 2010; Hoekstra et al. 2012) and in Supplementary Figure 1 (Prajapati et al. 2021). And yes, finding the signal end reliably is harder (often, *much* harder) this way, but that does not mean it should not be done.

In the following section, before explaining my claims in more detail, I provide a short summary of different ways that FP-signals have been analyzed in the literature.

A relatively short literature review

I truly believe that it would be very beneficial to analyze FP-signals as precisely as possible, even though it can be pretty challenging to reliably estimate certain parameters from these signals. MEA measurements, being less labor-intensive than patch clamp techniques, thus allowing much higher-throughput (Hwang et al. 2023), have several advantages such as the possibility to study cell-to-cell communication that plays a fundamental role in the biological systems (Kalmykov et al. 2019). FPD is analogous to the QT interval of ECG, and therefore, it is often used as an evaluation of cardiac safety of a new drug candidate (Clements and Thomas 2014). This means, that it can be possible to predict *in vivo* cardiotoxicity by analyzing how the studied drug impacts the FP (Cumberland et al. 2022). Also, as QT gives information about depolarization and repolarization (Yáñez de la Rivera, Soto-Bajo, and Fraguera-Collar 2018), tracking FPD as accurately as possible gives better estimation about these issues in *in vitro* cultures.

Based on my literature search, I would argue that the most common way to define FPD is from the first positive (high) peak to 2nd (repolarization) peak, basically **time between points 0' to 4' shown in Figure1**. (Gilchrist et al. 2015; Asahi et al. 2018; Tixier et al. 2018; C. K. Yeung et al. 2009; Clements and Thomas 2014; Hwang et al. 2023; Kalmykov et al. 2019; Hayes et al. 2019; Izumi-Nakaseko et al. 2017, 2023; Koivisto et al. 2022; Shi et al. 2021; Ando et al. 2017; Tertoolen et al. 2018) In some publications, FPD is defined from the first negative (low) peak to repolarization peak (Halbach et al. 2003; Reppel et al. 2004, 2007; Meyer et al. 2004; Egert and Meyer 2005; Kienast et al. 2014).

In some studies, the FPD end is the actual end of the repolarization wave, and its starting point is either the first positive peak (Dunham 2022), or something that is a bit unclear to me (Pradhapan et al. 2013; Shah et al. 2019) as they stated "*from the start of the*

depolarization wave". For example, I do not understand how these analyses would handle the FPD start with and without the first positive high peak. *If you know, please do not hesitate to reach me out and teach me!*

Instead of FPD, Riedel et al. (2014) used activation-recovery interval (ARI), and reported that as "*a robust, spatiotemporal measure of repolarization*". They even proposed "*the ARI as the gold standard measure of repolarization to most accurately define in vitro repolarization in MEA analyses of iPSC CMs*". I do see usefulness in ARI, but otherwise I disagree; in my opinion, the ARI does not reflect the full repolarization, as its end is defined at the point of maximum derivative of near the peak of the repolarization wave. In addition, as they state that the ARI measurement is a direct correlate of APD50, so it might not track e.g. EAD, thus I would argue that defining both, the ARI and FPD, would be more beneficial than only using the ARI. And, if I would need to pick only one, I would choose FPD.

While reading literature, I sometimes see contradiction between text and how FP-parameters have actually been defined. For example, Tixier et al. (2018) defined the end of the repolarization width (RW) as when the FP signal is returned to the baseline after the last peak (see Fig.2), but they still defined the end of FPD as the time point of repolarization peak itself, not when it is returned to the baseline. Also, Izumi-Nakaseko et al. (2023) stated that the repolarization ends when the 2nd peak is returned to the baseline (see Fig.1), but still they defined the FPD end as the repolarization peak. Gilchrist et al. (2015) proposed a new method to predict arrhythmic liability by defining the six-parameter arrhythmia assessment from FP-signals. These showed excellent predictive agreement with the known arrhythmogenic potential of the tested compounds. However, these were mainly related to beat intervals (time between two peaks between beats). Their FPD analysis did not consider returning of the repolarization, which I see important, especially if FPD is analogous to *QT interval of AP* (according to Kussauer, David, and Lemcke (2019) and their Table 1). Also, Egert and Meyer (2005) reported similar confusing results.

Understanding FP signals

I hope this short description will improve the understanding of extracellular FP-signals measured by MEA. For the background, it is highly recommended to understand the basics of the cardiac AP that is typically measured using patch clamp electrophysiology (Tertoolen et al. 2018). For typical AP-signals measured from *in vitro* hiPSC-CMs cultures, check e.g. Fig.2 by Ma et al. (2011) or Fig.4 by Prajapati et al. (2021). Firstly, inward cationic currents will result negative signals from the baseline, whereas inward anionic

currents or outward cationic currents will lead to positive signals (C.-K. Yeung et al. 2008). Because of that, depolarization will be seen as negative peak in FP-signal. This can be easily understood if you consider separately cases when the dominant cell is and is not the pacemaker cell; when the pacemaker cell is close to the measurement electrode, the FP signal has only a low peak, thus indicating that the electrical activity arose close to that electrode. On the other hand, if the signal has both positive and negative peaks, it indicates that the neighboring cell have been charged before the dominant cell on the electrode, thus showing the FP-signal propagation along the culture. To make things a bit more complicated, FP-signals may overlap in recordings from later stages, resulting in complex mixed waveforms. (Meyer et al. 2004; Egert and Meyer 2005)

If we simplify issues a bit, as illustrated in Figure3, we could say that the measured FP-signal consists of

1. Source, that is the AP-signal from the dominant, in other words the closest, cell(s). This is the actual signal that we are the most interested in.
2. Volume conductor, basically cell media and other surroundings issues around the electrode and the source cell(s).
3. MEA, including here the electrode and the junction resistance between the basal cell membrane and the electrode that is the main component of the electronic circuit (Tertoolen et al. 2018).
4. Amplifier, concerning all the hardware related to MEA amplifier that is used in the measurement.

Figure3: The structure of FP-signal (left figure from Tertoolen et al. (2018) which explains

the electrical components of the circuit): source (action potential from cell(s)), volume conductor, MEA-electrode and interfaces between the cell and the electrode, and amplifier.

To conclude, measured FP-signals have large differences in

- i) amplitude: measured beating amplitude can vary e.g. between 10 μV and 1 mV, and the noise level can be on the level of 10 μV
- ii) frequency: beating typically varies between 0-120 BPM, in other words 0-2 Hz; even 0 BPM can be "normal" when e.g. studying cardiac ischemia using hypoxia and reoxygenation (Häkli et al. 2021, 2022)
- iii) signal forms: "high and low peak" vs "only low peak", large differences in repolarization phases, and so on.

My Method

To gain the maximum usefulness of MEA measurements, it is a must to be able to reliably define certain parameters from FP-signals. Unfortunately, this is not always an easy task. Especially, if one is aiming for a fully automated analysis system that automatically and precisely defines all the desired parameters from a large amount of data. The challenge is that these FP-signals have high variability for several reasons; not only because of their origin is from different cell types with varying levels of differentiation (Hwang et al. 2023), how well the cell population is attached on top of the MEA and the distance between the cells and the actual MEA-electrode, but also because of the differences in the hardware that is used for recording FP-signals. For me, this type of a fully autonomous system, that would actually work with all different types of FP-signals that I have handled during these years, was a way too challenging task. Therefore, I developed a semi-autonomous method for *DatAnalyzer* that automates analysis as much as possible, but allows also human interaction for the sake of flexibility. Basically, the challenging FP signal is firstly divided into smaller pieces (= parameters defined from FP-signals) and combined together in the later stage; in other words, FP-signals are analyzed from the defined parameters (such as FPD and tdep), not directly from the raw FP-signal itself. Personally, I do not believe that AI/Machine Learning would be useful if directly used with raw FP-signals. There have been, and probably will be, people that have tried this without remarkable results that at least I would know. Yet, it is possible that one day they prove that I am wrong, but before that, I do see a huge potential for combining AI with methods to define important parameters more or less automatically as will briefly discussed be in [Future outlook](#).

My method is similar to the way that have been proposed earlier, except one main difference: the FPD end should be defined at the time instant when the FP signal returns back to the baseline, because only then we can fully track the RW and get the whole repolarization.

Therefore, my modified explanation to what has been stated (Halbach et al. 2003; Kienast et al. 2014) is following:

1. The first positive peak of the FP, in a propagating hiPSC-CM monolayer, corresponds to a contribution of neighboring, previously excited, tissue or cell.
2. The first negative peak of the FP relates to depolarization as it depends critically on Na^+ current.
3. The duration of the FP, FPD, is defined as the time from the start of the depolarization to the end of the repolarization. In actual implementation, typically 10% difference is used as a baseline level to trigger the start or end.
4. Depolarization time, t_{dep} , is defined as a time between the start of the depolarization (10% below the baseline A_0 towards the negative peak) and the minimum of the depolarization wave. In actual implementation, this peak point is defined from the filtered signal, aiming to avoid the effect of noise on the results. More explanation is given in the figures below.

In Figure4, I show how a typical non-pacemaker cell signal should be analyzed.

Figure4: My opinion, how non-pacemaker FP-signals should be analyzed.

My opinion is, that the main reason why peaks are used to define FPD, is because it is so much easier to find these peaks than reliably estimate the starting and returning points of the signal. And therefore, this simplified definition has been used. In *DatAnalyzer*, this challenge is tackled by the following implementation:

1. find low peaks; if there isn't any, only high peaks, just turn the signal as explained in Section "Only high peak"
2. take part of signal around the found peak: starting point is x-time backward and end point y-time forward from the peak location (e.g. 150 msec and 1000 msec, respectively, like has been in Figure4)
 - (typically) add multiple signal parts from different low peaks together and average it (also e.g. mean of the signal could be considered)
 - For example, you might have 60 sec long measurement signal that includes 30 beats, so after you have found these 30 low peaks and taken 30 signal part of those --> then take average of them
3. From the formed signal, find depolarization (and FPD) start point 0'
 - define low peak value A_{low} (at point 1')
 - define baseline level A_0
 - define the peak amplitude A_{peak} : $A_0 - A_{low}$
 - from the low peak position, go backwards to point where the signal is (e.g.) 10% from the baseline: $A_0 - 0.1 * A_{peak}$
4. From the formed signal, find FPD end point 4'
 - Find repolarization peak location and value (3') A_{rep}
 - from the repolarization peak position, go forward to point where the signal is returned to (almost) baseline, for example, it is 10% from the baseline: $A_0 + 0.1 * (A_{rep} - A_0)$

In real-life signals, defining these points is not always easy even from the averaged signal as explained in the end of Section [Understanding FP signals](#). Therefore, in *DatAnalyzer* two different signals are used to define the depolarization points (0' and 1') and the repolarization points (3' and 4'). Basically, depolarization is defined from the signal that is filtered with a smaller moving median filter (default size is 30), whereas repolarization points are defined from the end part of the signal that is filtered with a larger moving median filter (default size being 100).

No high peak → pacemaker cell

FP-signals from pacemaker cells are different from signals generated by other cell types as has been shown a long time ago (Meyer et al. 2004; Kolossov et al. 2005); they do not

have the first high peak at all (see e.g. Kolosov et al. (2005) and Fig.7). Therefore, in this signal case, t_{dep} and FPD should be analyzed as shown in Figure5. Same approach that was described in the previous section is used to define these important parameters.

Figure5: My opinion, how pacemaker FP-signals should be analyzed.

Comparison to AP signal

In the following examples, I use AP-signals from a study by Prajapati, Ojala, and Aalto-Setälä (2018) to show similarities between negative derivative of AP signal and typical FP signal. It is a known fact that the FP signal is similar to the negative derivative of the AP signal (Asahi et al. 2018). As can be seen in the following figures, the negative derivative of the AP (dAP/dt) signal has a very similar signal profile than the FP signal from pacemaker cells.

Figure6: Three different AP-signals and their negative derivatives. Signals are from Prajapati, Ojala, and Aalto-Setälä (2018).

Figure7: Zoomed AP-signals and their negative derivatives showing similarities with pacemaker FP-signals. Bottom inset shows one beating from Signal3 (Prajapati, Ojala, and Aalto-Setälä 2018). Blue line: AP-signal, Red line: negative derivative of AP.

Only high peak

In some cases, there is only high peak. There are several possible reasons for this, e.g. because of the distance between the dominant cell and the measurement electrode. In these signals, I would simply flip the signal and then analyze it as a pacemaker cell as was demonstrated earlier. Next figure presents this idea; measurement signal is flipped (in practical implementation, the values are just multiplied with negative one) and then analyzed as presented in Figure5.

Figure8: Flip “just-high-peak” signal before analyzing it.

Limitations

This work has focused on 2D cell cultures, but as there are differences between 2D and 3D cultured hiPSC-CMs, the FP analysis presented here might not be as easily as I hope to be extrapolated to the 3D model (Hwang et al. 2023). One could disagree with my claim, that the FP-signals with only positive peak should be flipped and then analyzed as a normal signal from a pacemaker cell. Notably, inspection of Figure8 (flipped) reveals a structural similarity to the pacemaker waveform in Figure5 — both show a slow pre-depolarization drift followed by a trough — providing empirical support for the inversion

approach within the data presented here. This internal observation has not yet been independently validated in other datasets or platforms. A practical criterion distinguishing distance-attenuation cases (where inversion is appropriate) from poor cell-electrode coupling cases (where electrode exclusion may be preferable, based on signal SNR and waveform shape) remains to be specified in future work. For example, Egert and Meyer (2005) stated that on those locations where this type of FP signals are measured, there is only minimal early depolarizing Na^+ and Ca^{2+} currents at this location, and passive, capacitive outward currents compensating inward currents simultaneously flowing at neighboring location. Someone could also point out, that I should not forget bioelectromagnetism (e.g. check Chapter 11 from book by Malmivuo and Plonsey (1995)³) when analyzing MEA signals. For example, by defining volume sources and volume conductors, could be the most proper way for analyzing FP-signals; however, that went over my expertise and might be just too challenging to implement in the big data scale that would really enhance FP-signal analysis.

Future outlook

As discussed before, measured FP-signals have large differences in their amplitude, frequency, and signal forms. Therefore, I do not personally think that using machine learning approaches directly with raw MEA data from cardiomyocyte cultures will work. And, as measured MEA signals consist of so many parts as described earlier in Section [Understanding FP signals](#), I neither see that any template approach, e.g. as presented by Pradhapan et al. (2013), can be a general solution for FP-signal analysis from different beating cardiomyocyte cultures.

Therefore, my own approach to classify and analyze signals would be

- i) (semi)autonomously find peaks from raw MEA data
- ii) extract parameters from these peaks, e.g. define amplitude and (average) peak duration (=field potential duration FPD)
- iii) then, using ML approaches for these extracted parameters, e.g. to classify signals

Defining discussed parameters from FP-signals (FPD, t_{dep} , several amplitudes and other time values, their change,...), modeling surroundings (MEA measurement hardware etc) and with use of AI, similarly to Juhola et al. (2022) with calcium signals, it might be possible to estimate the AP signal from the FP signal. Especially, if combining this analysis together with the method of creating pores in the cell membranes by electroporating pulses via the same MEA electrodes (Jurkiewicz et al. 2021; Hayes et al. 2019), as this could allow better estimation of the true AP signal. After that, analyzing the estimated AP signal could reveal much better information about the cell itself, thus

providing more detailed information how e.g. cells respon to certain drug. This idea is presented in Figure9.

Figure9: Proposed way to improve FP-signal analysis. If knowing different FP-signal parts precisely enough, it could be possible to reverse engineering to estimate AP-signal from the measured FP-signal.

I truly believe, that remarkably better *in vitro* studies could be done by combining more precisely FP-signal analysis to advanced cell culture systems. If we could reverse engineer the true AP signal from the measured FP signal, many new interesting *in vitro* studies could be performed when knowing both electrical propagation (from FP signal) and intracellular measurement (from FP-derived AP signal). For example, combining that with microphysiological systems (MPS) that are advanced *in vitro* platforms for modeling human or animal organ and tissue functions, we could study human organ and tissue level functions in health and in diseased states much more accurately than traditional methods. (Vuorenää et al. 2023) This could be a real alternative to animal models in basic research, drug development, and toxicology. Some of these new advanced MPS systems do not only provide a precise and stable environment, but also have possibility to mimic diseases, for example cardiac ischemia (Häkli et al. 2021; Häkli et al. 2022), by providing precisely controlled hypoxia conditions that has also potential to be used in cancer research(Tornberg et al. 2022). Also, it is mentioned that the optimal identification method to understand the mechanisms underlying the certain phenotype could be to integrate *in vitro* MEA recordings together with *in silico* cultures (Cerina, Piastra, and Frega 2023).

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1. Salute to Groucho Marx; if unfamiliar, just google "Those are my principles" groucho marx↩

2. *DatAnalyzer* is freely available in GitHub <https://github.com/AnaHill/DatAnalyzer>↩

3. Online version of the book is available in <https://www.bem.fi/book/>↩

4. Micro- and Nanosystems Research Group (MST Group): <https://research.tuni.fi/mst/>↩

5. Heart Group: <https://research.tuni.fi/heart-group/>↩